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PROSPLIGN

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Prospecting natural lignin biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules

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D7.1 – Preliminary Dissemination Communication and
Exploitation Plan

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Responsible Author	Zoi Volioti, Elettra Magni, Veronica di Lorenzo		
Contributions from	Vanessa Spadaro, Filippo Giancarlo Martinelli, Elina Roine, Brian Kelly		

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a **Preliminary Dissemination Communication and Exploitation Plan (DCE Plan) for the PROSPLIGN project**. The report describes specific dissemination, communication and exploitation methodologies, tools, channels and pathways in order for the project to reach its described objectives. The report is delivered with regards to deliverable **D7.1 ‘Preliminary Dissemination Communication and Exploitation Plan’** and serves as the basis for the elaboration and development of the next three WP7 deliverables in line:

- *Deliverable D7.2 – Mid project DCE plan and report (M16)*
- *Deliverable D7.3 – Final DCE Plan and Report (M35)*
- *Deliverable D7.4 – Plan for post project exploitation of project KER (M36)*

From Month 1 of the project, back in January 2024, the Magfi team (WP7 Leader) along with the help of the coordinator and the rest of the project partners have been working on assembling and assessing the relevant information in order to act upon and devise this preliminary DCE plan. Already ahead of the project’s Kick Off Meeting (KOM) in Dublin, February 2024, the Magfi team started with the project’s messaging and visual identity as well as the production of a detailed Dissemination Communication and Exploitation tracker in order to start off the discussions on the foreseen PROSPLIGN DCE activities, discuss the project’s needs and the particular partners’ considerations. The first PROSPLIGN press release was sent to a collection of relevant to the lignin valorisation media after the KOM took place and a wide and detailed stakeholders mapping and analysis is in place already laying out tangible exploitation pathways.

The document is comprised of **two separate but interlinked plans that will run in parallel and in intersection with each other during the project’s lifetime**. The first part of the report outlines **the preliminary Dissemination and Communication Plan (section 3)** and the second part describes the

preliminary Exploitation Plan (section 4). Together they form the whole PROSPLIGN Dissemination Communication and Exploitation Plan.

2. Background information to the project

The **PROSPLIGN** project - **PROSP**ecting natural **LIGN**in biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules - is a **European funded Research and Innovation Action** project. Our **key objective** is to apply state-of-the-art methodologies to prospect the bioactivity potential of lignin, a **natural, abundant and sustainable source material**. Our **mission** is to **discover new bioactive chemicals** derived from lignin and to **validate their potential** for application in the pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and fragrances markets.

Conventional lignin depolymerisation methods utilise **forcing conditions** which **destroy lignin's native rich chemical functionalities**; therefore its potential as a source for new bioactive chemicals is currently overlooked.

The PROSPLIGN team have designed an innovative set of research processes based upon **mild, selective depolymerisation methods** which **preserve** lignin's native chemical diversity – unlocking the door to explore **lignin as a resource for bioprospecting**. PROSPLIGN's mission will be achieved using a combination of cutting-edge processes including:

- Chemical and enzymatic methodologies for **mild and selective lignin depolymerisation**
- High-throughput bioactivity screenings to **identify** lignin-derived bioactives
- Processes for **isolation, purification, and characterisation** of bioactives
- **Bioactivity optimisation** and **validation** of bioactives for commercial application
- Optimisation of production routes with support from **multivariate data analysis**

Plant **lignins exist as randomly cross-linked polymers with highly variable structures** made up of carbon-oxygen- and carbon-carbon-linked phenylpropanoid subunits. The variable connectivity of these subunits expresses a **rich variety of chemical and structural functionalities** (including many associated with **bioactivity**), as well as chiral centres (chiral centres are points in a molecule which can exist in different 3D configurations which can exhibit different bioactivities). While the core phenylpropanoid-based scaffold is common in lignin from all plant specimens, different plant families and species express unique structural analogues and arrangements. Thus, **the potential for discovering unique chemical motifs from different lignin is vast.**

In addition, **dietary lignocellulosic biomass** (e.g., seeds or fruits) is already known to **contain bioactive molecules** (called *lignans*), albeit in tiny quantities, **with well-documented pharmacological effects**. Many of these molecules have close structural relationship to motifs identified within lignin polymers. This gives **further strong reasoning** to pursue a depolymerisation strategy to selectively liberate such bioactives from lignin polymers.

Over half of all drugs currently on the market have chemical structures with chiral centres. The importance of chirality in the pharmaceutical industry is understandable when one considers that the **different chiral isomers can exhibit different bioactivity**. From a synthetic/manufacturing perspective, the introduction of chiral centres into a molecule in the desired configuration is not trivial and can often be an expensive and tedious process: therefore an expansion of the pool of readily available chiral compounds through the selective depolymerisation of lignin presents an opportunity to **prospect for new bioactive compounds** – either directly or through **derivatisation**.

3. Preliminary Dissemination and Communication Plan

This section outlines the steps that need to be taken and the means that need to be used throughout the PROSPLIGN project in order for the project itself and its outcomes to be efficiently communicated to a wide spectrum of audiences. The rationale behind this preliminary PROSPLIGN Dissemination and Communications Plan is simple; **it outlines the steps that need to be taken in order to respond to four main dissemination and communication questions:**

- *What is the PROSPLIGN project about?*
- *To whom does the project need to be communicated?*
- *How will the project be communicated to its target audiences?*
- *When will each DCE activity will take place?*

3.1. Messaging – WHAT

Creating concise, simple to read and comprehensive messaging that **describes the project**, its vision and project plan, the partners involved in it, the particular lignin valorisation processes and research methodologies in place as well as the main research outcomes, **is the core action in order to set the basis for all other actions in a dissemination and communication strategy.** The Magfi team and the KelAda teams have already had at the beginning of the project a communications-focused discussion in order for Magfi to note any particular messaging styles or red communications flags the company has. It is important to note that since KelAda is the project's primary exploitation partner, the idea is to create messaging that the company - along with the rest of the consortium - will be able to use to sell its developed research products (in this particular project the identified bioactive molecules) past the end of the project. A project communications-focused discussion with the rest of the

project partners also took place during the project's Kick Off Meeting in Dublin, in February 2024, in order to explore any particular communications and branding issues the rest of the consortium partners may have and want or do not want to be included in the PROSPLIGN messaging.

3.1.1. Key messages

The very first step in any DCE plan is the development of a set of 5-7 key messages that will describe the project. The MAGFI team along with the close collaboration of the coordinating team (KelAda) has created 7 key messages that form essentially the basic description of the PROSPLIGN project, outlining what it is about, its comparative advantage, the unique set of research methodologies it puts in place, the research processes that are going to be utilised as well as the composition of the project's consortium. The following set of key messages is the general set to be used in all marketing tools and activities:

1. The **PROSPLIGN** project - **PROSP**ecting natural **LIGN**in biodiversity towards unlocking value-added bioactive motifs and molecules - is a **European funded Research and Innovation Action** project.
2. The **key project objective** is to apply **state-of-the-art methodologies to prospect the bioactivity potential of lignin** – a **natural, abundant and sustainable biopolymer component of lignocellulosic biomass**.
3. PROSPLIGN's bioprospecting workflows will focus on the identification of compounds and validation of their potential for **application in the pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and fragrances markets**.
4. The project's **comparative advantage lies within its core conceptualisation**. Traditional lignin depolymerisation methods utilise forcing conditions which destroy lignin's native rich chemical (and stereochemical) functionality and potential for bioactivity. The PROSPLIGN partners have designed an **innovative research set of processes to tackle the technical hurdles in the management of this complex polymer**.

5. After a **desk-based review and categorisation of the types and sustainable plant sources of lignin** to be explored, the consortium will analyse their bioactivity potential using a **combination of cutting-edge chemical and enzymatic depolymerisation methodologies, coupled with isolation and purification processes**, and **high-throughput bioactivity screening**. The consortium will also make use of **an extensive multivariate data analysis (MVDA)**.
6. A **preliminary Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Techno-economic Assessment (TEA)** of the developed value chains will provide the consortium with valuable feedback to support **optimisation of communication, exploitation and sustainability activities** of the project.
7. Four universities, two SMEs and a research institute **from six different European countries** form the project consortium. The partners include **KelAda Pharmachem** (Ireland), **University of Helsinki** (Finland), **Fundación MEDINA** (Spain), **NOVA University Lisbon** (Portugal), **University College Dublin** (Ireland), **Magfi** (Malta) and the **Bern University of Applied Sciences** (Switzerland).

After the initial call at the beginning of the project with the project coordinator and the realization that the project is **per se difficult to explain outside the market experts, the academic and scientific circles and the professionals working in the field**, KelAda offered a set of even simpler key messages that could be utilised **orally to communicate the project concept to students and the general public in day-to-day conversations**:

- The PROSPLIGN project is a European-funded research project focused on exploring the potential benefits of lignin, a natural substance found in woody plants, for various applications.
- Lignin can be thought of as the “glue” or “scaffolding” within plants which gives them support and structure. To do this job, lignin is a tough, complex substance made up a wide variety of chemical structures.
- The main goal of the project is to investigate how lignin could be used to create new and useful chemicals.

- Traditional methods of breaking down lignin often damage its beneficial properties. In this project, we're developing new techniques to break it down more selectively to preserve its potential benefits.
- We'll start by studying different types of lignin from various plants to see which ones have the most promise. Then, we'll use advanced methods to break down the lignin into smaller parts and test their potential benefits.
- Our focus is on finding new compounds derived from lignin that could be used in medicines, cosmetics, and fragrances.
- We'll also assess the environmental and economic impacts of our processes to make sure they're sustainable.
- The project involves collaboration between several institutions across Europe, each bringing different expertise to the table.

3.1.2. Questions and Answers

To complement the key messages and the essential introduction to the PROSPLIGN project and research processes, **a more extensive document with the project's background information has been produced in the form of Questions and Answers**. A Q&A document typically elaborates on the project idea and the product, the relevant market information, the regulatory framework covering the outcome product, the valorisation technologies in a more detailed and explanatory manner as well as the project's sustainability foundation.

The particular form was produced by Magfi in order to offer the consortium partners the opportunity to be in line with their responses to questions that are highly probable to rise during a conversation, a project presentation or a media request. The PROSPLIGN Questions and Answers **have also served as copy for the PROSPLIGN website and along with the project key messages complement the content for all visual and marketing tools, the script for the project video and social media posts** that were envisaged at the beginning of the project and the communications teams has already used and been using.

The questions that were further elaborated in the Q&A document are the following:

1. **Who are the PROSPLIGN partners collaborating to unlock the untapped lignin bioactive compounds' potential?**
2. **What is the process of bioprospecting referring to?**
3. **What is lignin?**
4. **What is a bioactive compound?**
5. **What is depolymerisation?**
6. **What are the depolymerisation methods that the PROSPLIGN project is going to utilise?**
7. **What is the throughput method the PROSPLIGN project is going to utilise?**
8. **What is a multivariate data analysis?**
9. **What is the sustainability and innovation potential of the project?**

You can **see the answers that were elaborated**, with the help from the respective partners involved in each process and task, **on the PROSPLIGN Frequently Asked Questions website page** here: <https://prosplign.eu/faq/>

3.2. Target Audience - TO WHOM

Defining the target audience - or target group/s - is a crucial step for any dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy. The target audience refers to the specific group of people, companies, organisations, associations, NGOs, think tanks, policy bodies, potential product buyers, etc. that are set in a DCE as **the receivers and multipliers of the messaging** surrounding the project.

Throughout the last five months, the Magfi team has mapped out – and will continue to add to the mapping - the stakeholders **involved in the lignocellulosic biomass research landscape and market** both on a European but international level too and its base now outlines **more than 200 stakeholders very relevant to the market.**

The stakeholders mapping allows for the development of a stakeholders list which is going to be used to drive dissemination and communications on the selected communications tools and social media platforms – for example finding, start following or even tagging a particular organization invested in lignin valorisation or a company within the project’s target markets (pharma, cosmetics, fragrances) in order to establish a two-ways communications pathway. The mapping is also essential for the identification of the project’s Exploitation Pathways (see following section 4.1 on the Exploitation Plan) and follow-up with potential exploitation partners for a successful market uptake.

The contact list has been developed following the GDPR rules and it is populated only with email addresses that are publicly available – mostly info@... emails that organisations use for general notifications and news receipt.

The **target audience includes organisations** across and around the lignin valorisation value chain such as:

- Biomass production (natural lignin feedstock providers)
- European and international green chemistry/tech players, start-ups valorising lignocellulosic biomass
- Institutions/research companies/universities/labs assisting in the valorisation process
- End users (aromatics, pharmaceuticals and cosmetics companies) who would/could use or are keen on using the defined-in-the-project bioactive compounds in their products
- Policy bodies/think tanks/associations that deal with biomass biodiversity, green chemistry
- Lignin producers’ associations
- NGOs covering themes that the project could have an added value to look into and keep a close account of (NAGOYA protocol, bioeconomy strategy, biodiversity)

- Consumer organisations that are supporting natural pharma, cosmetics, fragrances
- Scientific journals that could cover any of the aspects the research in the project will look into
- Other EU projects that are related to the PROSPLIGN research (almost all partners have for instance affiliated projects as presented during the Project's Kick Off meeting in Dublin, February 2024)
- Other non-EU projects the consortium could exchange knowledge, ideas or further expand its collaboration with
- Academic departments and research institutes with lignin in focus
- Magazines and online media
- Relevant to the project events (bioeconomy, biotech, lignin focused, natural cosmetics, fragrances, pharmaceutical event themes)

3.3. Communications and dissemination tools – HOW

The next step in devising a concrete and easy to implement PROSPLIGN dissemination and communication strategy, is to **identify the means, the marketing and communications tools and channels which can support mainly a Business-to-business (B2B) strategy since the project does not entail any ready-to-use consumer products.** **Business-to-business** refers to communication that is conducted between companies/organisations.

The following sections **outline the research ahead of, the actual selection of the B2B communications tools as well as their development,** to be utilised during the PROSPLIGN project based **on the description of Task 7.2 of the project's Description of Action.**

1.1 PROSPLIGN trademark background check and IP availability

Following the rationale and research that needs to be conducted ahead of any product or project communications tool development, the Magfi team conducted a thorough research on the existing use and the availability to register the project's name – PROSPLIGN – as a trademark. A preliminary analysis was performed during December 2023, ahead of the project kick off. The results of the search were discussed during the KOM in Dublin but the Magfi team ran the trademark registration check again following up the meeting.

The process included searches in Europe (including the UK), the USA, China, and some parts of Asia using various resources, including the **Intellectual Property Office UK**, the **United States Patent and Trademark Office**, the **World Intellectual Property Organization**, the **European Union Intellectual Property Office**, the **China National Intellectual Property Administration**, and [Marcaria](#) – a brand protection company that specialises in national and international trademark and domain registration services.

Based on the Magfi research the trademark "Prosplign" was available in all the searched regions. It is important to note at this point that we did find one software application using the name "Prosplign" registered in the United States. Notably:

- The software application did not appear to be a registered trademark. Although it uses the name "Prosplign," it may not have secured formal trademark protection.
- The software operates in a different International Trademark Class.

This means the potential for confusion between the PROSPLIGN project brand and the particular software is **likely minimal due to distinct product categories**. In the PROSPLIGN case the project name is not used in the same area of the PROSPLIGN programme/utility for computing the alignment of proteins to genomic nucleotide sequence. This concept is connected with the

following statement from the link shared by our Project Officer too on the IP matter we raised with her during the project KOM:

<Refraining from using an acronym similar to a registered trademark for goods and/or services in the same area is important, particularly when consortium partners intend to commercially exploit a result or provide a service in the market under the acronym or name of the project.>¹

The Magfi team shared the analysis with the coordination team and sent an additional email with the findings to the **European IP Helpdesk**, asking for further validation. The officer who responded to the Magfi project manager run an additional search on **TMView**, a database compiled by the **European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO)**, where there are trademark registrations from most of the main national IP offices in the world and includes all trademarks registered in Europe. The IPR officer with an answer to the Magfi inquiry validated our research results on 11/04/2024, found no particular registration that clashed with the project name and advised us to continue using the name PROSPLIGN for our project.

1.1.1 3.3.1. Project visual identity

A compelling yet simple and clean visual identity has been produced to cover all the PROSPLIGN visual tools and create the project's unique visual identity. All the visual elements were designed following the European Research Executive Agency design and brand guidelines and feature the EU emblem with

¹https://www.unipassau.de/fileadmin/dokumente/forschung/EU/projects_acronyms_trade_mark_preventing_risks.pdf

the funding phrase needed. The PROSPLIGN visual identity incorporates the following elements:

- **A project logo** – A logo is an easily recognisable graphic symbol that identifies a company, a commercial product, or any public or private entity or in this particular case an EU project. It is an essential graphic element that is part of the visual identity of a project.

Picture 1 - PROSPLIGN logo

- **A defined visual identity** – The product’s visual identity is all of the imagery and graphical information that expresses who a brand/project is and differentiates it from all the others. In other words, it describes everything the target audience can physically see - from the logo to the interior design of a store.

After a careful ‘Discovery Session’ the Magfi graphic designer elaborated three different project logos for PROSPLIGN. The Magfi team presented the available options at the project’s KOM in Dublin and the whole consortium voted to select the visual identity that felt most fitted for the project.

Based on the selected logo and its colour spectrum, the Magfi graphic designer developed the PROSPLIGN visual identity and used it in all the other visual and marketing tools and developed a specific brand guideline. A brand guideline is a comprehensive manual that outlines the visual and stylistic elements of a brand. It serves as a **reference for anyone involved in creating communications or materials** for the brand, ensuring that all elements are used **consistently and correctly**. By adhering to these guidelines, we ensure that the PROSPLIGN brand is presented uniformly across all platforms and media, reinforcing its identity and enhancing its recognition.

Picture 2 - PROSPLIGN stylescape

1.1.2 3.3.2. Marketing tools (dissemination materials)

The marketing tools the Magfi graphic designer along with the Magfi content creator worked on and produced include the following:

- **An A5 leaflet (flyer) –** Right after the logo decision, the Magfi team produced an A5 flyer with the project key messages and the consortium description in. The brochure has already been printed and

Picture 3 - PROSPLIGN A5 leaflet mockup

- **A three-fold brochure** has also been elaborated and contains the necessary project information and key messages. The project brochures has been designed as an online tool to be used on the website, shared on social media, shared through email etc. but also as a printed tool, to serve as a leave-behind at trade events and project presentations.

Picture 4 - PROSPLIGN three-fold brochure mockup

- **A roll-up banner** – A roll-up or pull-up banner, is a self-supporting advertising display comprising a banner – a wide strip of fabric or other material – with

Picture 5 - PROSPLIGN roll-up banner

content printed on it and a base into which the banner can be rolled up, making it all easy to carry around and use at events, product presentations, exhibition stands etc. The PROSPLIGN roll-up has a simple, fresh and mesmerising design and has been elaborated based on the project’s visual elements.

- **A factsheet** – A factsheet is usually elaborated on the basis of a product and it outlines its specific characteristics. The PROSPLIGN factsheet treats the project as the product at this stage as there aren't any tangible project products to display. Instead, the factsheet displays the project's process using the project's

Picture 8 - PROSPLIGN factsheet focusing on lignin

infographic and provides the consortium's reasoning on selecting lignin as its feedstock.

- **A project presentation** – A branded project presentation is a set of customised PowerPoint slides with the project's and product design style. The Magfi team has designed and populated a PROSPLIGN branded presentation with the

Picture 9 - PROSPLIGN ppt presentation's front slide

project logo and visual identity colours, the key project description and the partners in.

- **Social media templates** – Social media graphic templates are an image that businesses can use on various social media networks to help increase the organic reach of their posts. These graphics are typically branded, visually appealing and include some type of photo or vector graphic. Below you can

Picture 10 - PROSPLIGN website launch visual

see an example of the social media template and imagery that was produced to accompany the PROSPLIGN website launch post on LinkedIn.

- **A project video** – A project video is an explainer video that effectively demonstrates the idea behind it, its advantages, the benefits of its outcome product as well as the partners and in the PROSPLIGN case, its funding bodies (REA and EU). By using narrative and metaphor, a project video can create a better lasting impression in the consumer's mind, leaving the project's features to be experienced rather than explained. After a careful elaboration of the video script along with the coordinator, the Magfi designer put together an short and aesthetically pleasing video which depicts the key project description. You can see the video on YouTube here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bbBNXogcm8I>

Picture 11 - PROSPLIGN YouTube video screenshot

The materials produced will be updated - especially the project factsheet, the project presentation, the poster and the infographic of the project - according to the project development and its findings. At the final stage of the project additional dissemination materials will be developed to exploit specific result sand exploitation.

1.1.3 3.3.3. Project website

A professional website is essential in the modern business era as it is one of the primary touchpoints for all interested organisations, buyers, customers and prospects. The PROSPLIGN project website includes the key project description, the project's story, vision and mission, the consortium description, a FAQ page and also features the project contact details: <https://prosplign.eu>

Picture 12 - PROSPLIGN website homepage screenshot

1.1.4 3.3.4. Press releases, news articles, media outreach and trade media relations

A **press release** can be the cornerstone of a B2B communications campaign. It needs to have a captivating title, be short and precise and offer the journalist/editor a snapshot of the product description and a reason to publish it as 'news' in their publication. If a press release is compelling enough, there is a good chance it becomes a news story or a fully-fledged news article.

Media outreach is the process of increasing a company's/product's public exposure by connecting with journalists, editors, bloggers or social media influencers and partnering with them to promote your business on their platform. In a more traditional form, it is the process following a press release on the product launch, a new product production process, the issue of a patent, an award win, a partnership between two companies, a buy-out etc. It is essentially a round of contact emails and calls following up the launch of the product/company news in order to establish more exposure.

In a more proactive form, **media relations**, is the ongoing relationship and monitoring media process a communications/marketing manager may build in order to identify exposure opportunities early on. Publications and online media often set themes and invite the industry to produce content.

A research on publications and online magazines has shown the Magfi team that the specific trade media segment is limited. Below there is a list of the more specific bioeconomy/biomass/lignin publications which the Magfi team will approach in order to establish a relationship with and publish the project news:

- Green Chemicals Blog <https://greenchemicalsblog.com/about/>
- Il Bioeconomista <https://ilbioeconomista.com/about/>
- Renewable Carbon News <https://renewable-carbon.eu/news/>
- JRC Digital Media Hub <https://visitors-centre.jrc.ec.europa.eu/en/media>
- Biomass Magazine <https://biomassmagazine.com/contact>
- BE Sustainable Magazine <https://www.besustainablemagazine.com/>
- EurActiv <https://www.euractiv.com/sections/energy-environment/>
- Agro & Chemistry <https://www.agro-chemistry.com>
- Platform Bioeconomy (PBE) <https://platformbioeconomie.nl>
- Awe International <https://www.awe.international/magazine>
- CHEMAGAZÍN - magazine for chemical-technology and laboratory practice
<https://chemagazin.cz/en/info>
- Chemical Engineering <https://www.chemengonline.com>
- CHEManager International <https://www.chemanager-online.com/en/news>
- Inside Sustainability <https://inside-sustainability.com>
- Cosmos Magazine <https://cosmosmagazine.com>
- Chemistry World <https://www.chemistryworld.com>
- Chimica Magazine <https://www.chimicamagazine.com/it/index.do>

The **first PROSPIGN press release has been published following the project's KOM in Dublin, in February and can be seen here:**

<https://prospign.eu/kicking-off-a-e3-4-million-project-on-lignin-bioprospecting/>

1.1.5 3.3.5. Articles in scientific publications

Publishing project and product research, process production, a product's ingredients effectiveness results, etc in renowned scientific journals in order to obtain scientific support, can be critical for a project and its product credibility in a communications and dissemination strategy. The list of scientific publications that the project could publish its results in will be elaborated further down the timeline of the project as partners start obtaining their first results.

1.1.6 3.3.6. Events

In today's market, there is a greater demand to provide an opportunity for face-to-face or virtual meetings to ensure that any identified community can have the ability to interact, obtain new information on the lignin valorisation sector and new products. The consortium has already been in two events promoting the project, networking with professionals and keeping accord of the trends in the market:

- The fifth [BIOKET international conference](#) (19-21 March 2024, Reims, France) which was organised by [Bioeconomy For Change](#) and brought together innovation, technology and sustainability professionals to boost new businesses working into biomass valorisation and looking into developing high added value products.
- [Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking \(CBE JU\) Info Day 2024](#) (23 March 2024, Brussels, Belgium) which is an opportunity to gain insights into the CBE JU call for proposals, have a better understanding of the whole application process, learn from and interact with other – relevant to the PROSPALIGN project scope - project participants.

Picture 13 - Malachi and Filippo attending BIOKET 2024

Both events were attended by Dr. Malachi Gillick-Healy (KelAda team) and Filippo Giancarlo Martinelli (Magfi team) communicating the project's mission with key stakeholders.

The project partners have already registered for two other major bioeconomy events taking place at the end of June 2024. KelAda is expected to attend the 32nd European Biomass Conference and Exhibition (24-27 June, Marseille, France) and Magfi is expected to attend World Bio Markets (26-27 June, The Hague, The Netherlands).

1.1.7 3.3.7. Collaboration with other EU projects

It is common among EU projects to form 'communications collaborations' in order to disseminate their results either during each other's communication activities or on their online media. The Magfi team has identified a number of EU funded projects with which it can seek synergies to promote the PROSPLIGN project and learn from their respective outcomes. Additionally, the companies, associations, organisations, etc that form the respective consortia constitute the stakeholders' scenery the project needs to communicate its results too.

1.1.8 3.3.8. Social Media Strategy

Taking into consideration the **duration and content of the project (36 months)**, the **Project Grant Agreement (PGA)** as well as the **media guidelines**, this section outlines the strategy that will cover the effort put forward to **communicate the project**, its outcomes and partners' involvement **outside the consortium on two particular social media platforms during the years 2024, 2025 and 2026.**

The selected PROSPLIGN social media platforms are **LinkedIn, with the creation of a dedicated PROSPLIGN LinkedIn Page and X (formerly known as Twitter) with the creation of a dedicated PROSPLIGN X account.**

Setting clear social media goals

The first step to any marketing and this particular case, social media strategy, is figuring out what the project wants to achieve through its interaction on social media. Taking into consideration the project's research concept, the communications guidelines put forward by Horizon Europe, the Research Executive Agency and the content of the PGA, the PROSPLIGN social media goals are to:

- ⇒ **Communicate the project** on the most relevant platforms outside the project consortium and its partners, notably **LinkedIn and X**
- ⇒ **Establish a double-route communications interaction** with the lignin stakeholders
- ⇒ **Generate leads** for further research partnerships and down the road the exploitation and commercialization of the analysed bioactive compounds
- ⇒ **Drive the PROSPLIGN website traffic**
- ⇒ **Build awareness on the PROSPLIGN project**
- ⇒ **Gain further insight on the lignin valorisation research and market trends and news**
- ⇒ **Discover possible events that the project can be presented, or the project partners can participate**

Target audience

As indicated and elaborated in section 3.2. *Target audience*, the identification of the right target audience is a crucial step for the communication strategy and by extension the dedicated PROSPLIGN social media strategy: it refers

to the specific group of people, companies, lignin producers, organisations, associations, NGOs, think tanks, policy bodies, potential end-product buyers, etc. that are set as the receivers and multipliers of the messaging surrounding the project.

Content creation

The Magfi team will prepare a **content database** that will be shared with the partners through SharePoint, notably a Social Media Plan with all the content that will be posted on LinkedIn and X. The rationale for building the content for the PROSPLIGN social media posts will revolve around these themes:

- Project Kick Off Meeting
- Launch of the PROSPLIGN landing page
- Launch of the dedicated PROSPLIGN website
- Description of the project and its innovative set of research processes
- Description of the project's sustainability aspect
- Description of the partners involved in the project (the project team)
- Launch of the PROSPLIGN project video
- Sharing lignin and biomass valorisation market trends and insights from validated news sources and academic research (i.e., consumer trends and perception, market growth projection numbers, other brands that accelerate the growth in the lignin market, etc.)
- Sharing events that are relevant to the project thematic
- Sharing events partners will attend in 2024/2025/2026 with an invitation to join them at their booths/stands/presentation slots, etc.
- Sharing events/trainings/seminars/webinars the project partners organise within the project
- Sharing further project news/outcomes/findings as the project progresses
- Sharing PROSPLIGN project articles that have been profiled in publications, magazines and online media
- Sharing project press releases and news items

- Sharing information/photos from presentations at events the partners have attended

Living in the era of fake news the market news and research results the PROSPLIGN accounts will share need to **be a) valid and credible and b) newsworthy**. For these reasons the news sourced and shared will be from the listed publications above and the organisations identified in the thorough stakeholders' analysis the Magfi team has performed.

Posting frequency

Finding **the right day and time to post content** is crucial for any social media strategy and its successful implementation.

There is a trend that seems to be validated by most of the platforms studies and that is that posting on Tuesday, Wednesday and Thursday mornings work well for most cases. Based on the current research and its conclusions, it is therefore decided that the optimal days to post on LinkedIn and X are **Tuesday, Wednesday and Thursday between 7am-12pm with two posts per week**. More frequent posting can be anticipated around the project's events as well as the events the consortium attends.

The Magfi team will also test between days and times and **follow the LinkedIn, X, and Hootsuite analytics programmes** to determine and accordingly adjust the timing that works best for the particular PROSPLIGN audience.

Direct Messages

LinkedIn offers the opportunity to look for the particular company departments and job descriptions fitting the target audience identification described above. Messaging directly a Purchasing Manager or a Researcher of a targeted company or organisation for instance is a common practice and often proves fruitful in establishing at least a first point of contact and widen the lead generation basis.

The Magfi team will look for the organisations listed on the stakeholders mapping on LinkedIn as well as X, follow the most relevant people working in those organisations and eventually direct message (DM) the most active on the platforms in order to establish contact and communication on behalf of the project and/or indicate to KelAda (as exploitation partner) potentially relevant ones for exploitation activities, hence supporting the synergetic work of dissemination/communication activities (Magfi) on one hand and exploitation/replication ones (Magfi and KelAda) on the other. Further details on this point will be elaborated jointly by Magfi and KelAda in due time, also taking into account the level on engagement obtained within the targeted social media.

3.4. Timeline – WHEN

It is fundamentally important to make the project, the developed technologies, the end-products and their technical benefits and increased sustainability widely known both to the related industries, among the whole value chain, and potential customers, as well as the general public as potential end-users of the final products utilizing the beneficial formulation with biobased bioactive motives and molecules. The communication activities will **thus run continuously throughout the project** in order to promote the exchange of information between the project and all the related stakeholders and communities. During the first period of the project, activities will focus on creating a more general awareness on the project's vision and mission and connection to the respective EU policies through the main stationery and marketing communications tools development. As soon as initial research results are available, the consortium will be able to focus on more detailed dissemination activities as well.

An overview of the main communication tools is provided along with the association of each tool with the respective target group and the respective KPI/timeline of accomplishment, connecting the dots between **the “HOW”, the “TO WHOM” and the “WHEN”** questions stated early on in the document above.

Abbreviations reference: Scientific community and academia (**SC+A**), Feedstock providers (**FP**), Target (applications) markets (**TM**) – Pharma, Cosmetics, Fragrances, Policy makers, policy bodies, NGOs (**PM+NGOs**), End users: general public, citizen and consumer groups (**GP**).

Tool	Target Group (TG)	Measure/KPI/Timeline	Check
Logo & Visual Identity	ALL	Developed by M4	Done
Presentation	SC+A, FP, TM, PM+NGOs	Developed by M4	Done
Website	ALL	5,000 visits by project end / Developed by M4	Launched
Roll-up banners	ALL	2 project roll-up banners/ One developed by M4	One general project banner developed
Brochure	SC+A, FP, TM	1 brochure / Developed by M4	Two developed – one A5 leaflet and one three-folded brochure

Infographic	ALL (simple enough to be understood by GP)	1 infographic	Done
Video	ALL (simple enough to be understood by GP)	1 video/2,000 YouTube/Vimeo views at the end of the project	Done
Social media	ALL (content simple enough to be understood by GP)	Twitter/X: 400 followers LinkedIn: 400 stakeholders / Launched by M4	Done
Webinars	SC+A, FP, TM	As needed during the duration of the project	
Other media for website	ALL	At least 20 publications/news pieces for website at the end of the project	3 news pieces uploaded by M6
Newsletters	SC+A, FP, TM, PM+NGOs	3 newsletters/ one per year	
Press releases and media outreach	SC+A, FP, TM, PM+NGOs	At least 3 press releases during the project	First press release sent after the KOM (February 2024)
Joint events, workshops, round tables	SC+A, FP, TM, PM+NGOs	1 event/year At least 40 participants/event	Ideas for planning the first PROSPIGN event include a stakeholders' engagement event either in Malta or Brussels with the

			collaboration of REA
Final conference	ALL	1 final event at M36	
Events participation	SC+A, FP, TM, PM+NGOs	At least 5 events/year starting after M12	5 relevant events attended already by M6
Direct contacts	FP, TM	At least 100 potential feedstock providers and companies by the end of the project	

4. Preliminary Exploitation Plan

4.1. Introduction to exploitation and methodology

The Exploitation Plan is developed for the purpose of understanding how to make the best use of the results produced during the project also beyond the project's duration, and to push forward the opportunities deriving from it, in the context of the DCE activity.

The first step of an Exploitation Plan is to understand which are the main results that would derive from the project and that could be further exploited, the so called "Key Exploitable Results" (KERs). The phase of the KERs identification is made up of several moments: indeed, the KERs that are directly produced from a project can come from a pre-existent KERs inventory, already elaborated at the time of preparation of the project before submission, or can be discussed once the project is started, in appropriate moments as the consortium meetings or via dedicated meeting. In this case, some of the "most natural" KERs had been already identified during the

proposal development stage; a first list was further discussed and drawn down during a dedicated session held in person at the kick-off meeting as part of the WP presentation.

On the basis of this list, a first mapping of relevant stakeholders interested in one or more of these first PROSPLIGN KERs is carried out: they will be contacted during project implementation for exploitation purposes. In fact, the PROSPLIGN project has been intentionally designed from the beginning to actively involve relevant stakeholders guaranteeing measurable project impact. In order to obtain successful engagement, it is essential to take proactive steps to establish connections with individuals and organizations from all of the identified stakeholder groups.

The first step for the Stakeholder Mapping is building a strong database of stakeholders and their contacts, which will be the main means of communicating project details and can be useful for identifying important recipients who share PROSPLIGN goals, to build connections and promote cooperation between the PROSPLIGN consortium and other pertinent organizations. The process of creating this database starts with desk research to find pertinent companies and other EU funded projects to create involvement between large well-known players across sectors. It is necessary to compile and continuously update a dynamic database, and to identify stakeholders in accordance with PROSPLIGN target groups, as well as competitors and facilitators in parallel.

In fact, a thorough database of stakeholders will make communication with all parties involved in PROSPLIGN easier by consolidating contact information and categorizing stakeholders based on their degree of involvement with the project. Various dissemination and exploitation strategies will be used depending on stakeholders' degree of involvement.

Magfi's plan in terms of developing both Stakeholders and KERs databases is as follows: firstly, collecting data on the basis of internal research, then the stable version of both the Stakeholders Mapping list and the KERs list is shared with the coordinator firstly and then to all the consortium (removing email contacts) for further validation, and for checking if further important elements are missing. In parallel the list of KERs is set to be further expanded. The expanded KERs inventory is sent for validation to the coordinator and to the consortium. This process will be repeated during the project implementation as both KERs list and Stakeholders database are live documents.

The KERs list and Stakeholders database are conceptually and practically interconnected for the whole duration of the project. In fact, the stakeholder list will be, during the years of the project, expanded and most important used to approach, in alliance with the communication and dissemination activities, specific targets and understanding what their feedback is. The KERs list will be also fine-tuned during the project implementation, being refined as the project produces concrete and relevant results from a commercial point of view. In turn, the updated KERs list will be used to expand or to refine the stakeholders' database, while the feedback of the target will be used to generate either leads or to improve the value proposition of the KERs.

From approaching the targets and from looking at their response, it is possible to obtain learnings for the improvement of the value proposition of each KER or can obtain achievement in terms of lead generation for the KER itself. The main theoretical framework at the basis of the core activities here are based on the AIDA (Awareness, Interest, Desire and Action) method. The AIDA model is in fact considered the best-known marketing model amongst all the classic marketing models.² This model identifies cognitive stages an individual goes through during the buying process for a product or service: this is to be visualised as a "purchasing funnel" where buyers (in this case party interested in a specific project KER) goes to and for at each stage, to support them in

² Smart Insights, The AIDA Model. (2023) ([URL](#))

making the final “purchase” (such as in this case: decision to engage contractually with the KER holder). Many marketers find AIDA useful, and somehow the AIDA funnel could be referred to as a communications model rather than a decision-making model. In fact, companies use AIDA to identify how and when to communicate during each of stage of their customer journey: so, using this model would help in planning tailored and targeted communication campaign. This approach was selected based on its strategy and its demonstrated effectiveness.

4.2. KERs inventory

As briefly explained in the methodology, the KERs inventory has been developed in many steps.

The most natural KERs have been identified already during the proposal development phase, before the submission, and they were appropriately refined and drawn down during a dedicated session of the live kick-off meeting. Such starting KERs are listed below:

- **KER 1 – 2: molecule #1 and #2** - molecule showing the strongest and/or most interesting bioactivity/functional property from the bioactivity assays relevant for **pharma applications**.
- **KER 3 – 4: molecule #3 and #4** - molecule showing the strongest and/or most interesting bioactivity/functional property from the bioactivity assays relevant for **cosmetic applications**.
- **KER 5 – 6: molecule #5 and #6** - molecule showing the strongest and/or most interesting bioactivity/functional property from the bioactivity assays relevant for **fragrance applications**.
- **KER 7: detection method** - method and/or novel combination of detection/screening techniques to specifically detect bioactive compounds within a complex mixture.

- **KER 8: separation and purification method** - method to specifically separate a molecule from a mixture and purify it as much as possible, without affecting its bioactivity.

After the project kick-off, the KERs inventory has been further expanded and iterated upon also in light of iterative exchanges of feedbacks between Magfi, the coordinator and the rest of the consortium. The expanded list is provided in the following paragraph.

4.3. Key Exploitable Results

The KERs inventory will be “a-work-in-progress” list, as KERs will evolve as the project results manifest themselves. In fact, any KER inventory, should be processed/updated based on many criteria as likelihood of success, real market potential, or it may be expanded according to the project developments and results. At the date of the report, the KERs inventory list looks like as follows (starting KERs #1-#8; unforeseen/secondary KERs #9-#15):

- **KER 1 – 2: molecule #1 and #2** - molecule showing the strongest and/or most interesting bioactivity/functional property from the bioactivity assays relevant for **pharma applications**.
- **KER 3 – 4: molecule #3 and #4** - molecule showing the strongest and/or most interesting bioactivity/functional property from the bioactivity assays relevant for **cosmetic applications**.
- **KER 5 – 6: molecule #5 and #6** - molecule showing the strongest and/or most interesting bioactivity/functional property from the bioactivity assays relevant for **fragrance applications**.
- **KER 7: detection method** - method and/or novel combination of detection/screening techniques to specifically detect bioactive compounds within a complex mixture.

- **KER 8: separation and purification method** - method to specifically separate a molecule from a mixture and purify it as much as possible, without affecting its bioactivity.
- **KER 9: detection method, depolymerisation** - method and/or novel combination of analytical techniques to quickly determine quality/yield/performance of lignin depolymerisation methods.
- **KER 10: bioprospecting pipeline** - combination of methods and reaction pathways (enzymatic, chemical or both) that depolymerise lignin into a complex mixture from which bioactive compounds are identified/purified/characterised and whose bioactivity/functional profile are validated for specific application sectors.
- **KER 11: derivatisation method** - combination of synthetic chemistry methods to prepare chemical derivatives - e.g. derivatives of lignin-derived bioactives - with the aim of emphasizing/tuning specific functionalities and bioactivities (and/or adding new ones).
- **KER 12: sustainable production route** - efficient and sustainable production process designed to obtain a specific bioactive molecule starting from lignin (and/or a lignocellulosic biomass) or with a retrosynthetic approach.
- **KER 13: by-products (mixture of not bioactive lignin)** - mixture of lignin fragments (and other) as remaining from isolation and purification steps. Lignin can be evaluated for its energy content, or as filling material.
- **KER 14: libraries from high-throughput screening (and/or statistics)** - collection of a complex set of data (and/or statistics), as coming from the many high-throughput screening assays, that can inform many R&D processes on the probability of obtaining specific motifs in molecules deriving from specific starting lignins and specific combinations of techniques.
- **KER 15: Method to obtain a functional/suitable formulation** - any method and/or formulation that ensures stability and/or bioavailability and/or processability (at industrial conditions) of the final molecule - per sé or into a final product (not state-of-art) - i.e. combination of innovative drying, essication, but also derivatisation techniques.

The table in the next page describes for each KER the characteristics of the results, the sector of application and the benefits that they may bring to the users:

Table 1 - Preliminary KERs list

#	Name	Type	Potential user / market	Benefits
1-2	Molecule #1 and #2	product	pharmaceutical production and healthcare sector	bio-based, clean-label, fossil-free benefit of taking advantage of lignin's natural chemical complexity to discover novel bioactive motifs, as an alternative to drug discovery methods using brute-force <i>ab initio</i> synthesis and screening to find new drugs
3 - 4	Molecule #3 and #4	product	pharmaceutical production (i.e., overlap with medicated/functional cosmetics), cosmetics production/formulation and healthcare sector	bio-based, clean-label, fossil-free benefit of taking advantage of lignin's natural chemical complexity to discover novel bioactive motifs, as an alternative to brute-force <i>ab initio</i> synthesis
5 - 6	Molecule #5 and #6	product	fragrance sector (but also cosmetic sector, using fragrant ingredients in their final products), "air freshener" market	bio-based, clean-label, fossil-free benefit of taking advantage of lignin's natural chemical complexity to discover novel bioactive motifs, as an alternative to brute-force <i>ab initio</i> synthesis

7	Detection method	patent / license	companies offering analytical and screening services; any company producing bioactive ingredients by extraction from complex matrix (with a product development department)	specificity, sensitivity, effectiveness possibility of identifying compounds with unique functional properties worth for unforeseeable target market
8	Separation & Purification method	patent / license	any company producing bioactive/functional/specific biobased compounds derived from biomass; but also, analytical and third-party companies offering services in line with/similar to this phase of the production process	optimized process (in terms of time and resources) that does not affect the activity. Also permits identification of potential hit compounds which would not be isolable using other methods due to poor separation or low abundance.
9	Detection method - depolymerisation	patent / license	companies offering analytical and screening services; any company extracting/depolymerizing lignin or other complex biopolymers. Lignin valorisation R&D.	a fast and effective method to measure the progress of lignin depolymerization.
10	Bioprospecting pipeline	patent / license	any company producing ingredients from lignocellulosic biomass with a product development department. Any company who has an interest in	novel combination of processes which permits enhanced/novel potential for the discovery of bioactive/functional compounds.

			discovering and/or marketing bioactive molecules. Any company who has an interest in identifying novel/high-value applications for biomass. Any company who has an interest in enhancing the valorisation potential of biomass.	
11	Derivatisation method	patent / license	any company producing (bioactive) ingredients with a product development department. Any company interested in licensing synthetic chemistry methodologies.	novel combination of process which allows to emphasize a specific bioactivity and/or to add a specific feature to a bioactive molecule (i.e., stability, bioavailability, ...)
12	Sustainable production route	patent / license	any company producing bioactive ingredients with a product development department; any third-party company offering manufacturing services in the field (i.e., CDMO)	efficient, optimized in its working conditions, sustainable under all the three levels (economic, environmental and social) and scalable, to reach production volumes of industrial relevance
13	By-products (mixture of not bioactive lignin)	product	any industry that burns lignin for energy; manufacturing	circularity, no wastes, no EoL, low (or zero) cost

14	Libraries from high-throughput screening (and/or statistics)	product	pharma, cosmetics, F&F sectors - any company producing ingredients from lignocellulosic biomass with a product development department	the set of data and statistics allows to save time, moneys and resources in the lab research and the process development (and screening?) phases
15	Method to obtain a functional/ suitable formulation	patent / license	pharma, cosmetics, F&F sectors - any company producing pharma/cosmetic/food/etc. bioactive ingredients	the method allows to obtain a bioactive ingredient that is stable, bioavailable, and processable at industrial conditions

4.4. Exploitation pathways

4.4.1. Main target markets

The long road to commercializing novel bioactive compounds is frequently characterized by a high failure rate among candidates to achieve desired levels of safety and efficacy. Commercialized bioactive substances usually combine a variety of structural patterns and chemical functionalities requiring multiple steps in their synthesis. Finding promising lead compounds requires synthesizing and screening a wide range of chemical derivatives even though some chemical structures are known to have bioactive characteristics.

Biologically active compounds customized for particular purposes are needed by numerous industries and as demand is predicted to grow in the upcoming years these compounds will become more and more valuable in a variety of markets such as pharmaceuticals (worth 1.37 trillion euros) cosmetics (worth 80 billion euros) and fragrances (12 billion euros). A triple-bottom-line approach that takes into account social environmental and economic issues is in line with meeting this demand with bio-based environmentally friendly and renewable molecules. Agricultural aquaculture bioremediation and cosmetics are just a few of the industries that have benefited from bioprospecting—the search and identification of new biological resources with financial or industrial potential.³

Exploring the natural chemical diversity provides access to a large pool of new chemical structures that are ready for bioactivity screening. PROSPLIGN aims to perform bioprospecting in the vast terrestrial natural resource of lignocellulosic biomass with a focus on its largely unexplored lignin fraction which is known to contain a multitude of bioactive and functionally diverse small molecules.

Techniques for isolating bioactive compounds from lignin polymers with selectivity have not yet been developed to the point where the intended

³ The botanical explorer's legacy: a promising bioprospecting tool. (2017) ([URL](#))

markets can profitably be served by them. By utilizing a synergistic combination of cutting-edge chemical and enzymatic depolymerization techniques PROSPLIGN seeks to overcome this difficulty. PROSPLIGN will work to find companies from target markets to verify the interest in the output of the project in order to guarantee applicability.

Initially the consortium will focus on pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and fragrances markets. Exploring key players within the European Union a spectrum of companies was taken into consideration for each market from well-established entities renowned in their respective field to lesser-known companies that prioritize sustainability and circular economy.

Specific results of PROSPLIGN could also benefit target markets with new formulated products with advantage to conventional ones due to lignin origin, novel and improved bioactivity profile and sustainability and values. Even though each market will enjoy these benefits, each one also possesses intrinsic peculiarities and a unique profile that must be considered to enhance and characterize the applications that the PROSPLIGN project will have within that specific market.

4.4.2. Stakeholder analysis (detailed analysis): targets, facilitators and competitors

The exploitation activities of the PROSPLIGN project include promoting the most promising Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to relevant target markets, identifying potential targets. Preliminary main target market is the bioprospecting and biodiscovery segment of the pharma industry, followed by equivalent segments within the cosmetics and fragrances field. A natural “alternative market” may derive from the approaching of lignin producers, ideally technology/biorefinery owners, who may have an interest in obtaining higher value from their streams.

In order to search for main players in the European landscape dealing bioprospecting in pharma, cosmetics and fragrances sector the approach was

to use methodology and benchmark provided in Description of the Action (DoA), focusing on ones with great interest in research and development and in sustainability. The research also took into account the pre-contacted end user and similar companies.

The below graphs show some of the data collected in the stakeholder's database, identifying the role of them in respect to every KER. The companies classified as "**Target**" are those that could be interested in the results of PROSPLIGN project. Conversely companies that are labelled as "**Facilitators**" are either connected to communities or have knowledge in certain field which allows them to effectively share PROSPLIGN findings. While "**Competitors**" are businesses that are presently conducting research in the same and/or related areas and are actively involved in the market and that may be offering solutions in competitions to the ones promoted by the project. Every company, regardless of its classification, can play a role in promoting the impact and spread of the PROSPLIGN project.

A first contact with the companies will be established using various channels, from email, LinkedIn and contact page.

This initial contact will then be further developed and deepened with the aim of achieving a potential exploitation agreement for PROSPLIGN results at a pre-commercial level, in line with the project TRL and action type (in this case Horizon Cluster 6 RIA). A "business development"-like mindset will be maintained, prioritizing valuable feedback and potential joint development agreements over purely sales-focused interactions.

Figure 1 illustrates the geographic distribution of the current considered stakeholders, indicating the unique nations or regions they are from. This visualization facilitates the identification of the diversity and worldwide presence of the stakeholder pool.

Figure 1: geographic distribution of different organisation collected in the stakeholder database.

In Figure 1 it is possible to observe that France and Germany have the highest presence in the stakeholders' database, with a significant representation of the target group. These results align also with the project aim of engaging primarily with European companies. Facilitators have notable presence in France and United Kingdom and to a lesser extent in other countries while competitors are more evenly distributed but still with higher counts in France and the United States.

Figure 2 gives a comparative evaluation of stakeholders from EU countries as opposed to the ones from non-EU countries, confirming the distribution between higher represented target companies and less represented facilitators and competitors. In fact, these first two graphs (Figure 1 and Figure 2) already show a predominant presence in the database of target companies and, at the same time, EU players, coherently with the Exploitation Strategy that Magfi is developing for the PROSPLIGN project.

Figure 2: comparison between Target, Facilitator and Competitor from EU countries and ones from non-EU countries.

Figure 3 categorize stakeholders based on their scale of operation, differentiating among multinational groups, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), start-ups and research performing organization. It is worth it to note that while in EU countries SMEs are more represented the same is not true in non-EU ones. Multinationals are well represented in both group whereas Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) and startups are little to not represented at all.

Figure 3: comparison of stakeholders by their scale of operation, divided into EU and NON-EU

Figure 4 breaks down the market sectors every stakeholder operates in, providing insights into the specific areas of the market where PROSPALIGN project can deliver innovation and results. Consistent with the consortium's decision to initially focus mainly on the pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and fragrances markets, these sectors are well represented in the stakeholders' database, as well as all other sectors that work near or directly overlap with them, such as chemical and biotechnology.

Figure 4: comparison of stakeholders by market sector, divided into EU and NON-EU

In the subchapter 4.4.3 “KERs” this comprehensive overview of stakeholders will be broken down based on their potential involvement in exploiting different results from the PROSPALIGN project.

4.4.2.1. Potential feedstock providers

Another target group collected in the stakeholders’ database is identified as “**Potential feedstock provider**”: these companies, which include those from industries such as pulp and paper but also chemical and biorefineries, are relevant in the stakeholders’ mapping since they could benefit of the uptake of their residue products, with the opportunity to open up new market and participate in new value chains, contributing to biobased projects.

In detail, Figure 5 highlights various key aspects of these companies. It not only identifies the different market sectors in which these companies operate but also delineates the scale of their operations. Furthermore, it provides

information regarding the geographical location of their headquarters, specifying whether they are situated within an EU country or not. This level of detail is useful to understand the potential impact and relevance of each company in the context of PROSPHIGN project.

Figure 5: comparison of potential feedstock providers by sector and scale of operation, divided into EU and NON-EU

4.4.3. KERs

1.1.8.1 KER 1 – 2: molecule #1 and #2

The anticipated outcomes for KERs 1 and 2 are molecules exhibiting the most intriguing and potent functional property relevant to pharmaceutical applications. The pharmaceutical market in Europe is largely dominated by well-established multinational corporations alongside numerous small to medium-sized enterprises, primarily focused on the production of Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs). Both multinationals and SMEs industries may show interest in the outcomes of the PROSPHIGN project.

In the graphs below are showed some of the data collected in the stakeholder's database, focusing on organization involved in the market of molecule #1 and #2.

Figure 6: geographic distribution of stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 1-2

Figure 7: comparison between Target, Facilitator and Competitor from EU countries and ones from non-EU countries for stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 1-2

Figure 8: comparison of stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 1-2 by their scale of operation, divided into EU and NON-EU

Figure 9: comparison of stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 1-2 by sector, divided into EU and NON-EU

1.1.8.2 KER 3 – 4: molecule #3 and #4

The goal of KER 3 and 4 is to find the compounds derived from depolymerized lignin mixtures through bioactivity tests that have bioactivity or functional qualities that are pertinent to cosmetic uses. Skincare companies that might

be interested in these bioactive compounds are the main focus of the stakeholder mapping for organizations involved in KER 3 and 4.

In the European landscape of cosmetics sector some multinationals companies producing skin-care products stand out but it's worth taking in consideration smaller companies that place a particular focus on the use of bioactive compounds obtained by natural resources and with an active role in circular economy.

In the graphs below are showed some of the data collected in the stakeholder's database, focusing on organization involved in the market of molecule #3 and #4.

Figure 10: geographic distribution of stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 3-4

Figure 11: comparison between Target, Facilitator and Competitor from EU countries and ones from non-EU countries for stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 3-4

Figure 12: comparison of stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 3-4 by their scale of operation, divided into EU and NON-EU

Figure 13: comparison of stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 3-4 by sector, divided into EU and NON-EU

1.1.8.3 KER 5 – 6: molecule #5 and #6

The KER 5 and 6 are molecules showing the strongest and most interesting functional property from the bioactivity assays relevant for fragrance applications.

The fragrance industry is an essential link in a long and intricate value chain that extends from suppliers of ingredients to manufacturers and retailers of consumer products. The demand for sustainable and niche fragrances and perfumes has noticeably increased in the European fragrance market. Niche brands speak to customers looking for something different by specializing in providing unique artisanal scents created with premium ingredients. At the same time due to ethical and environmental concerns there is an increasing demand for sustainable fragrances. From ethically sourcing natural ingredients to using environmentally friendly packaging materials sustainable perfume brands place a high priority on eco-friendly practices throughout their production processes. Additionally, they aim to use renewable energy sources and cruelty-free vegan formulas to lessen their environmental impact.

In the graphs below are showed some of the data collected in the stakeholder's database, focusing on organization involved in the market of molecule #5 and #6.

Figure 14: geographic distribution of stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 5-6

Figure 15: comparison between Target, Facilitator and Competitor from EU countries and ones from non-EU countries for stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 5-6

Figure 16: comparison of stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 5-6 by their scale of operation, divided into EU and NON-EU

Figure 17: comparison of stakeholders involved in the market of KERs 5-6 by sector, divided into EU and NON-EU

1.1.8.4 KER 7: detection method

The following figure provides an overview of companies potentially interested in KER 7, therefore in a method or a combination of screening techniques to detect bioactive compounds within a complex mixture. Some of these companies offer screening and analytical services while others produce bioactive ingredients by extracting them from complex matrices. Moreover, in constructing the database, companies from different fields working with these ingredients were also considered. With their technologies to analyse and screen compounds these companies work together with biotechnology, nutraceutical and pharmaceutical businesses.

Figure 18 provides data regarding companies involved in the market of KER #4, comprehending an overview of the different market sectors they work in, their scale of operation and information on whether the company's headquarters is located in a country that belongs to the European Union or not.

The figure illustrates a diverse array of stakeholders across numerous market sectors, with chemicals, pharmaceuticals, plant-based ingredients, and

flavours and fragrances standing out. European SMEs are the most prominently represented.

Figure 18: comparison of stakeholders involved in the market of KER 7 by sector and scale of operation, divided into EU and NON-EU

1.1.8.5 KER 8: separation and purification method

The following figure presents an overview of companies potentially interested in KER 8, namely method to separate a molecule from a mixture and purify it without affecting its bioactivity. In the construction of the database were taken in consideration companies specialized in separation and purification of molecules from complex mixtures but also analytical and third-party services that work in this stage of the purification process. Moreover, the research has been expanded to companies that already offer solution for optimizing lignin recovery from biomass since PROSPLIGN project aims to expand and improve

actual methods to deal with lignin separation and purification. Furthermore, since the project will also approach the lignin depolymerization through enzymatic approaches also companies working in this field are included in the analysis.

Figure 19 provide data regarding companies involved in the market of KER #8, comprehending an overview of the different market sectors they work in, their scale of operation and information on whether the company's headquarters is located in a country that belongs to the European Union or not.

The figure also shows distribution of stakeholders across a high number of market sectors, with cosmetics, chemicals, and pharmaceuticals standing out. Both SMEs and multinationals are well represented.

Figure 19: comparison of stakeholders involved in the market of KER 8 by sector and scale of operation, divided into EU and NON-EU

The research work performed on stakeholder mapping and the identification of KERs was running simultaneously the last six months. This preliminary research, the figures and their explanations matching the particular KER(s), follow the descriptions of KERs 1-2, 3-4, 5-6, 7 and the description of KER 8.

The rest of the KERs identified in the process and the discussions with the project consortium (9-15) will not only be cross-checked with the existing stakeholders but a further, more in-depth and focused research will be conducted on each of them in the coming months as well.

4.5. IP and KERs ownership

Within EU funded projects, results (foreground) are normally owned by the partners who generate them within the project, while background is owned by the original party who owned it before the start of the project. Within PROSPLIGN, the results and backgrounds are regulated by Consortium Agreement (CA) and Grant Agreement (GA), specifically via the below articles and attachments:

- article 8. “*Results*” of the CA
- article 9. “*Access Rights*” of the CA
- attachment 1: “*Background included*” of the CA
- article 16. “*Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) — Background and Results — Access Rights and Right of Use*” of the GA
- annex 5 of the GA

As part of the exploitation strategy, a number of project results will be selected as Key Exploitable Results (KER), as indicated in the preliminary KER inventory, and further updates. For each of such KER, a tentative exploitation pathway is defined towards the target group, coherently of the strategy chosen by the KER owner. Importantly, KER owners are not automatically and univocally defined from the task descriptions, but rather the partner with the strongest/most obvious claim to ownership of a specific KER emerges directly from the GA/CA, although this is only an indication of potential KER ownership. The final/official owner of each KER will be established by the relevant Consortium’s governing body, the General Assembly, which will firstly establish the modality of KER inventory/ownership definition and then

validate the final KER inventory and the final KER ownership, although this procedure itself is subject to change/fine-tuning by the relevant consortium body.

For this aspect, further clarifications and elaborations will also be provided as part of deliverable D1.2 *“Preliminary Data Management Plan (DMP)”* by the PROSPIGN Coordinator.

5. Annex

5.1. Table of EU projects related to the PROSPLIGN scope

Project Name	Description	Status
<u>CIRCULIG</u>	Lignin is a naturally occurring material which gives trees structural support and helps them build resistance to biochemical degradation. The forest industry currently burns the majority of lignin in their energy and chemical recovery processes. Funded by the European Research Council, the CIRCULIG project aims to use lignin as a building block for materials that can be recycled, thereby extending the life cycle of forest products. Researchers will investigate new synthesis and assembly approaches to overcome obstacles to lignin use, focusing on improving solvent stability and functionality of lignin nanoparticles, and generating lignin fibres incorporating inorganic and metal nanoparticles. CIRCULIG will open new frontiers for sustainable lignin-based materials that can be recycled, which combine functionality and design.	Ongoing
<u>LIGNICOAT</u>	Sustainability is not limited to the materials with which items are made, it also embraces the various coatings that many of them rely on. This is why the sustainability in coatings looks at energy and resource conservation, waste minimisation or efficiency. It also involves the use of renewable and non-toxic products. In this context, the EU-funded LIGNICOAT project is exploring the use of lignin, which has a high potential in terms of cost and environmental benefits. Specifically, it will propose new synthetic routes to produce lignin-derived	Ongoing

	bioresins for coatings. The project's overall aim is to demonstrate technical, economic and environmental viability.	
<u>LignoMBB</u>	Funded by the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions programme, the LignoMBB project seeks to address raw wood shortage in the EU. To this end, it will develop a technology for producing mycelium-based biocomposites (MBB), using recycled and decontaminated wood. LignoMBB also plans to utilise lignin, a by-product from pulp mills, to enhance mycelial growth on the substrate. This is expected to improve the mechanical properties of the MBB. Agricultural residues will not be used, ensuring food security is not compromised. LignoMBB will seek applications for large volumes of old contaminated wood and develop novel MBB for structural applications. It will also measure volatile organic compound emissions at different stages of the MBB cycle, considering that MBB production can decrease these emissions.	Ongoing
<u>VIOBOND</u>	Phenol-formaldehyde resins are versatile synthetic polymers, with a wide range of industrial applications ranging from vehicle component production to furniture manufacture. However, the raw materials for manufacturing these resins are fossil-based. The EU-funded VIOBOND project will create the first commercially viable resin plant, producing phenolic resins that will partially substitute the fossil-based phenol and formaldehyde with lignin-derived raw materials. This flagship plant will produce around 45 000 tons of resin per year that could be used for plywood furniture	Ongoing

	and coating, sandpaper adhesives and glass wool thermal insulation binders. The project will demonstrate the efficacy of the resin production process and a business model for valorizing and transforming lignin in Europe.	
<u>FRACTION</u>	<p>The EU's drive towards a circular economy has seen increasing numbers of biorefineries established in Europe. As a result of the EU's bioeconomy, these will continue to rise; however, in future the focus will be on so-called 'second-generation' refineries, which target lignocellulosic feedstocks from non-edible and non-energy crops, as well as biowaste, to produce biofuels for electricity, heat, as well as bio-based polymers and chemicals. However, lignocellulosic feedstocks pose particular challenges to process. The required pre-treatments for the feedstock make biorefineries difficult to run economically; this is compounded by different feedstocks requiring different processes. If future lignocellulosic biorefineries want to remain competitive, they will need to be adaptable and capable of optimising production to a wide and changing range of feedstocks, demand and economic conditions.</p> <p>The FRACTION project will pioneer a new second-generation biorefinery approach. This is designed to maximise the purity and quality of lignin and hemicellulose side streams to allow them to be used in high added-value products, while keeping high quality cellulose as main targeted product. This relies on novel organosolv fractionation process based on γ-valerolactone (GVL) and water followed by downstream processing and purification</p>	Closed (May 2024)

	<p>technologies.</p> <p>The added value of this process arises from the performance of the GVL-based approach, which solves many of the existing challenges. It allows for continuous biomass feeding, high biomass loading and low degradation of all three streams – cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. In addition, the GVL is recoverable and recyclable. This technology should help ready second-generation biorefineries for the future.</p>	
<u>SWEETWOODS</u>	<p>The SWEETWOODS project aims to develop a first-of-its-kind biofractionation flagship plant in Estonia that uses sustainable hardwood biomass. The process combines innovative pre-treatment technology with enzymatic solutions to provide sugar recovery levels of over 90 per cent with exceptionally high-quality lignin. Sugars and lignin can be further processed and converted to high-value biomaterials capable of replacing fossil-based chemicals in a wide range of products.</p> <p>The project, which uses wood processing residues as a feedstock, will lead to wood-based biomaterials being produced on an industrial scale for the first time.</p>	Closed (May 2024)
<u>EUCALIVA</u>	<p>Lignin from pulping processes represents a major source of underexploited material with an estimated 17 million tonnes of lignin available from pulping processes across Europe. However, much of this lignin is simply burned onsite to provide steam for heat and power production. EUCALIVA aims to create a whole value chain from lignin, using Eucalyptus waste as its</p>	Closed

	<p>source. The project’s main focus will be to increase the efficiency, yield and cost-effectiveness of technologies through new approaches.</p>	
<p><u>GreenLight</u></p>	<p>Carbon fibre’s exceptionally high strength to weight ratio offers numerous advantages for many applications. However, it is expensive to produce, and the cost has restricted its use to relatively rarefied sectors such as aerospace, high-end automotive construction and wind energy.</p> <p>The GreenLight project will demonstrate a value-chain for creating a new bio-based, renewable and economically viable carbon fibre precursor – lignin – that will be produced in Europe with European raw materials.</p> <p>These precursors will be suitable for processing into carbon fibre and structural carbon fibre composites and make those more affordable and accessible, particularly in mass-market vehicles.</p>	<p>Closed</p>
<p><u>GreenSolRes</u></p>	<p>Levulinic acid has long been identified as a versatile ‘green’ chemical precursor for many applications. It is widely recognised as a platform substance for chemical synthesis and is seen as a key element in moving Europe towards bio-based manufacturing.</p> <p>However, to make that a reality, there has to be adequate production to meet demand at a realistic price. GreenSolRes will demonstrate the commercial viability of converting lignocellulosic biomass to levulinic acid or one of its esters for</p>	<p>Closed</p>

	<p>the manufacturing of solvents and adhesive resins with added-value and/or functionalities.</p> <p>The successful completion of the GreenSolRes will pave the way to the first commercial plant for sustainable production of levulinic acid (at 50 kta), and its derivatives, leading to a rapid gain in spectrum and production volume of bio-based consumer products.</p>	
<u>GRETE</u>	<p>The GRETE project aims to develop new and better technologies for wood pulp modification, cellulose dissolution and fibre quality generation complying sustainability requirements and market needs.</p> <p>Currently the raw material base to produce man-made cellulose fibres is limited, as only dissolving grade wood pulps are used commonly. The project will tackle this by widening the sustainable raw material basis for man-made cellulose fibres by including paper grade pulps. In addition, the solvent systems used to produce commercial man-made cellulose fibres are based on toxic and explosive chemicals; the GRETE processing technologies will increase safety, sustainability and feasibility of man-made cellulose fibre manufacturing.</p> <p>The issues addressed by the project play a significant role in developing sustainable and green technologies for the European industry. The partners of the project are strongly committed to face the challenge and achieve the ambitious results, supported by a dedicated stakeholder group with the aim to foster strategic decision-making.</p>	Closed

<p><u>LIBERATE</u></p>	<p>Lignin is one of the most abundant organic polymers on Earth, exceeded only by cellulose. Its depolymerization into value-added products would yield great environmental benefits. The EU-funded LIBERATE project aims to convert low-cost lignin feedstock from wood into high-value and sustainable chemicals through an electrochemical process. For this, it will deliver a pilot-scale electrochemical plant to demonstrate lignin conversion into chemicals such as vanillin and mixed phenolic derivatives, currently stemming from fossil energy sources. By developing the electrochemical lignin biorefinery, LIBERATE will help Europe move a step closer to a circular economy model – making the energy industry less dependent on imported oil and reducing its environmental footprint.</p>	<p>Closed</p>
<p><u>LIBRE</u></p>	<p>The global carbon fibre based composites market is worth an estimated €25 bn. However, using fossil resources to produce the main precursor for carbon fibre, polyacrylonitrile, has limited production capability and high costs. In addition, it depends on finite resources. This means that the development of an alternative source of polyacrylonitrile, using innovative and novel bio-industrial feedstocks and processes, has huge potential to deliver an economic win-win.</p> <p>The LIBRE project will utilise lignin-rich side stream feedstock from the pulp and paper industry, blended with a biopolymer precursor fibre, to create a more resource-efficient and sustainable carbon fibre production process.</p>	<p>Closed</p>

	The ultimate aim of the LIBRE project is to create carbon fibre materials with a superior structure that will open up potential new markets.	
<u>LigniOx</u>	The aim of the LigniOx project is to demonstrate the techno-economic viability of the unique LigniOx alkali-O ₂ oxidation technology for the conversion of various lignin-rich side-streams into versatile dispersants. High-performance concrete plasticizers will be the target end product, but potential other end uses, such as dispersants for paints and gypsum, will be evaluated as well. Valorisation of lignins originating from kraft and organosolv pulping as well as from 2nd generation bioethanol processes will be addressed. Both the oxidation technology and the end-product performance will be demonstrated at operation conditions, thus enabling industrial process installations and entry of the novel lignin products into the markets after the project. The valorisation of lignin side-streams will significantly improve the cost-competitiveness and resource efficiency of lignocellulosic biorefineries. It will also create low-cost, sustainable raw materials for the chemical industry. The LigniOx technology can be integrated into lignocellulosic biorefineries, or it can be operated as a stand-alone unit by chemical industry. For scale-up and process demonstrations, a mobile pilot unit will be constructed. The viability of the process concepts will be demonstrated in operational conditions using relevant pilot equipment and process modelling. The performance of LigniOx concrete plasticizers will be demonstrated by field tests, and industrial product prototypes will be produced. Techno-economy as well as environmental and socio-economic impacts will	Closed

	be assessed. Also, regulatory issues will be considered to ensure the market entry.	
<u>PROVIDES</u>	<p>PROVIDES will develop a new, sustainable and techno-economically feasible pulping technology for wood and agro-based lignocelluloses. Using a new class of solvents, known as deep eutectic solvents (DES), offers the ability to reduce process energy intensity at least 40% and investment costs by 50% over existing chemical pulping technology.</p> <p>DESs have the unique ability to dissolve, and thus mildly fractionate, lignin, hemicellulose and cellulose at normal temperature and pressure, allowing for further processing into high added value materials.</p> <p>The overall aim of PROVIDES is to provide tools that encourage radical innovations and a move towards low-energy mild pulping processes, which provide high quality cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin fractions.</p>	Closed
<u>SElectiveLi</u>	<p>Lignin accounts for about 20-30 % of the content of wood, and it is the second most abundant organic molecule on Earth after cellulose. During sulfite pulping of wood in the paper and pulp industry, the lignin is sulfated yielding water-soluble lignosulfonates (highly branched ionic polymers) as a by-product. The ability to valorise these biopolymers by converting them into organic monomers and other polymers for the chemical industry has many benefits. These range from greener chemicals to a circular economy with reduced waste, energy and raw material usage. The EU-funded SElectiveLi project will develop the technology to convert low-cost lignosulfonate</p>	Closed

	feedstocks into high-value, bio-sustainable chemicals.	
<u>SmartLi</u>	<p>SmartLi aims at developing technologies for using technical lignins as raw materials for biomaterials and demonstrating their industrial feasibility. The technical lignins included in the study are kraft lignins, lignosulphonates and bleaching effluents, representing all types of abundant lignin sources. The raw materials are obtained from industrial partners. The technical lignins are not directly applicable for the production of biomaterials with acceptable product specifications. Therefore, pretreatments will be developed to reduce their sulphur content and odour and provide constant quality. Thermal pretreatments are also expected to improve the material properties of lignin to be used as reinforcing filler in composites, while fractionating pretreatments will provide streams that will be tested as plasticizers. Lignin is expected to add value to composites also by improving their flame retardancy. The development of composite applications is led by an industrial partner. Base catalysed degradation will be studied as means to yield reactive oligomeric lignin fractions for resin applications. The degradation will be followed by downstream processing and potentially by further chemical modification aiming at a polyol replacement in PU resins. Also, PF type resins for gluing and laminate impregnation, and epoxy resins will be among the target products. Full LCA, including a dynamic process, will support the study. The outcome of the research will be communicated with stakeholders related to legislation and standardization.</p>	Closed

<u>SSUCHY</u>	<p>The SSUCHY project seeks to contribute to developing bio-based composite products with advanced functionalities and high structural properties for transportation sectors and in high value market niches.</p> <p>It will create opportunities to expand market applications for bio-based composites to semi-structural and functional applications in ground transportation and aerospace along with new opportunities in high value niches such as acoustics and electronic sectors.</p> <p>It aims to exploit the intrinsic and differentiating properties of plant fibres and bio-based polymers to develop and enhance the functionalities of bio-based composites.</p>	Closed
<u>UNRAVEL</u>	<p>The UNRAVEL project aims to develop advanced pre-treatment, separation and conversion technologies for complex lignocellulosic biomass. The technology relies on pre-extraction, fractionation using low-temperature acetone and subsequent downstream processing to isolate and convert the lignocellulosic constituents into high-value applications. This will produce usable lignin fragments and monomeric sugars from the cellulose along with a hemicellulose fraction suitable for biochemical conversions.</p> <p>It will bring together specialists with expertise of the entire value chain from feedstock composition, chemical pulping and pre-treatment, enzymes production, polymer chemistry, separation and reactor engineering, techno-economic and sustainability assessments</p>	Closed

	and knowledge dissemination, exploitation and communication.	
<u>WoodZymes</u>	<p>Many wood processing techniques require extreme conditions of heat and alkalinity. WoodZymes seeks to develop extremozymes (enzymes that can function under extreme environments) and extremozyme-based processes that will allow underutilized lignin and hemicellulose fractions of kraft pulp mills to be valorised. This will produce high-value bio-based compounds to be used as bio-equivalents of existing petroleum-based chemical building blocks and precursors.</p> <p>In doing so, they will create substitutive components (lignin-based phenolic resins and polyols) for the manufacture of medium-density fibreboards (MDF) and polyurethane (PU) insulation foams, potentially reducing or avoiding the use of toxic ingredients, whereas the sugar-derived compounds will be used as fibre bonding enhancers in papermaking. WoodZymes illustrates the potential of extremozymes in the global bio-based economy, contributing to the sustainability and competitiveness of cellulose and fibreboard and polyurethane manufacture.</p>	Closed
<u>Zelcor</u>	<p>Lignocellulosic feedstocks (dry matter plant biomass) are commonly used in the production of biofuels and bio-based chemicals. However, a major disadvantage of these feedstocks is the presence of substantial amounts of lignin, an aromatic polymer that is difficult to break down. This so called "recalcitrance" means lignocellulosic feedstock is often considered</p>	Closed

	<p>primarily as a waste product, utilised to produce energy through burning.</p> <p>The Zelcor project intends to demonstrate the feasibility of transforming lignocellulose recalcitrant side streams (lignocellulosic residues from ethanol production, lignins dissolved during pulping and lignin-like humins formed by sugars conversion) into high added-value bio-based products, including fine chemicals. This will be achieved by combining chemical and enzymatic catalysis with insect-based bioconversion.</p> <p>Demonstrating of the project's feasibility will be performed by process scaling-up, formulation of end-product prototypes and value chain sustainability and safety assessment.</p>	
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5.2. Table of events

EVENT	DATE	LOCATION	WEBSITE
CLIB International Conference CIC202 - Biomanufacturing a greener future	21-22 February 2024	Düsseldorf, Germany	https://www.clib-cluster.de/en/veranstaltung/clib-international-conference-cic2024/
BIOKET 2024 - The Bioeconomy Key Enabling Technologies	19-21 March 2024	Reims, France	https://bioket.tech
CBE JU Info Day 2024	23 April 2024	Brussels, Belgium	https://www.cbe.europa.eu/infoday24
Argus Biomass Conference 2024	23-25 April 2024	London, UK	https://www.argusmedia.com/en/conferences-events-listing/biomass/register
46th Symposium on Biomaterials, Fuels and Chemicals	28 April - 1 May 2024	Alexandria, Virginia, US	https://www.simbhq.org/sbfc/
The 28th Annual Green Chemistry & Engineering Conference	2-5 June 2024	Atlanta, Georgia, US	https://www.gcande.org

BIO 2024 - BIO International Convention	3-6 June 2024	San Diego, California, USA	https://convention.bio.org/about-bio
World Bio Markets 2024	26-27 June 2024	Fokker Terminal, The Hague, Netherlands	https://www.worldbiomarkets.com
EUBCE 2024 European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	24-27 June 2024	Marseille, France	https://www.eubce.com/eubce-in-brief/
Lignin Gordon Research Conference 2024 - Realizing Lignin's Potential in Biorefining by Bridging Biology, Chemistry, and Engineering	14-19 July 2024	Boston, MA, US	https://www.grc.org/lignin-conference/2024/
SMART 2024 - Sustainable Materials Research Summit 2024	21-24 August 2024	Helsinki, Finland	https://www.helsinki.fi/en/conferences/smart-2024/programme
XXVIII EFMC International Symposium on Medicinal Chemistry 2024	1-5 September 2024	Rome, Italy	https://www.efmc-ismc.org

Nordic Wood Biorefinery Conference (NWBC) 2024	15-17 October 2024	Örnsköldsvik, Sweden	https://www.ri.se/en/news/calendar/nordic-wood-biorefinery-conference-nwbc-2024-0
10th Biorizon Annual Event on Bio-Aromatics	TBA	TBA	
ICLECMC 2024: 18. International Conference on Lignin for Energy, Chemicals, Materials and Composites	18-19 November 2024	Paris, France	https://waset.org/lignin-for-energy-chemicals-materials-and-composites-conference-in-november-2024-in-paris

